

The Strategic Role of Human Resources and Empowerment Through the Commitment of the Government in Alleviating Poverty on Fishermen Society Coastal of South Minahasa District Indonesia

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Abstract

The strategic role of human resources is challenging changes came fast and widespread problem. The government's commitment is needed to support the fishermen seashores especially those that are in the South Minahasa District. This study aims to analyze the strategic role of Human Resources to Government Commitment, Empowerment to Commitment and Strategic Human Resources to Empowerment and Government Commitment in alleviating Poverty. Research conducted at the Fishermen Society Coastal South Minahasa regency. The population in the implementation of the research is Fisherman working on the coast numbered around 250 fishermen. This research was taken precision sampling 5% to maintain a representative of the study sample. Sample of 153 people. The analysis techniques used in the study using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The results of this study indicate that the strategic human resources positive and significant effect on the commitment of the command for 0.714. Empowerment positive and significant impact on the government's commitment for 0.873 as well positioned for empowerment human resources positive and significant effect of 0.34. The government's commitment to alleviate poverty in coastal communities should be carried out by providing a wide range of access to the right information, there needs to be accountability and the involvement of coastal fishermen in decision-making.

Keywords: Human Resources Strategic; Empowerment; Government Commitment; Poverty Alleviation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Changes in the business environment have an impact on the strategy human resources. Various effects of changes occur demands the attention of the Government of South Minahasa district, to be open to change and seek to draw up a policy strategy in tune with the changing business environment. The strategic role of human resources is challenging changes came fast and widespread problem. The government's commitment is needed to support the fishermen seashores especially those that are in the South Minahasa District. Development of human resources planned and organized with proper management will save natural resources, or at least the processing and use of natural resources can be efficient and effective. The development objectives in terms of interdisciplinary models there are three, namely: Development is in humans, the development of which are friendly to the environment, the development of government governance / good management (Widyahartono, 2010). Development of human resources is defined on two levels: first, developing a personal level regarding the development of the ratio, functional skills and system value. Second, the development of related macro related to personal empowerment of human resources like education, nutrition and health. National development policy so far failed to give adequate attention to the gap also raises some negative impact on regional

development, among others: the accumulated economic activities in certain areas, such as the growth of metropolitan cities and large uncontrolled resulting decline in environmental quality urban areas; the widening development gap between urban and rural areas; increasing per capita income gap; there are still many poor areas; lack of linkages between urban development activities in rural areas; as well as the neglect of the development of border areas, coastal areas and islands.

Fishermen as an important part in the process of improving human resources that need to be considered. Because so many of the coastal fishermen are in South Minahasa District of marginalized and underappreciated and perform life activities traditionally make efforts without equipped with adequate resources. Based on this study, the researchers formulate problems:

- i) Do Empowerment affect the government's commitment to alleviate poverty
- ii) What is the strategic role of Human Resources affect the government's commitment 3. What is the strategic role of human resources has a relationship with the empowerment

Human Resource Management is necessary for any organization that wants to achieve the desired objectives. Along with the emergence of human management needs, the paradigm shift towards human resource management functions occur from time to time. During the study of human resources by the government tend to be simply done and attention on government organizations and physical development while to pay attention to the poor who have limited human resources less attention. One of them concerned the government to provide human resource development in the relatively poor fishermen. Understanding of the importance of human resource management is increasing in line with the change in environment. The government's commitment is needed to support the fishermen seashores especially those that are in the South Minahasa District.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Strategic Role of Human Resources

The strategic role of Human Resources make an important contribution in the planning of business strategy. This means the achievement of the strategic role of human resources are appropriately starts from the analysis of human resource competencies and behaviors of human resources. Successful implementation requires a thorough analysis and understanding of the core in the formulation and planning. The final planning of a sustainable competitive advantage lies in the quality (Sunarto, 2005). Achievement of the strategic role of human resources can be done with several stages of the connecting role, enabling role, a monitoring role, innovating role and adapting role. Connecting role, the relationship between the role of human resources in business roles, the desires of the business, where implementation and which channel it so that it can be accepted. Increase involvement as a key element in the strategy of leadership problems. Enabling role, the customer; featuring a whole in business studies internally and externally to the organization to be the main customers of the organization. Monitoring role, the use of computer technology and human resource information systems. Innovating role, contributing the use of assessment on the measurement of efficiency and effectiveness in human resource development. Adapting role, the use of flexible role model at the bureaucracy Schuller & Hauber in Usmara (2003).

2.2 Empowerment

Community empowerment program has become mainstream efforts to improve the welfare and poverty alleviation. With empowerment, the development does not start from the nadir, but originated from something that already exists in the community. Empowerment means what has been owned by the public is that development resources should be developed so that more real usefulness to the community itself.

2.3 Government Commitment

The prolonged economic crisis provides a very broad impact in the development of national economy. Economic development has been less transparent, making it less foster participation among the community. Inequality productive economic asset holding structure results in gaps in various aspects of life, be it social, cultural, political and other social aspects. The government's commitment is needed to alleviate poverty. The government's commitment made in the form of commitment to honesty, commitment to fairness, commitment to accountability and commitment of trust. All of this should be built in implementing sustainable development.

2.4 Poverty

Basically, the definition of poverty can be seen from two sides, namely: a). Absolute poverty, poverty is associated with official estimates of income and needs are only limited to basic needs or minimum basic requirement that allows one to live decent lives. Poverty is measured by comparing the income level of people with income levels needed to obtain the basic needs of food, clothing and housing in order to ensure its survival. b) the relative poverty, poverty seen from the

aspect of social inequality, because there are people who are able to meet the minimum basic needs but still far lower than the surrounding communities (UNDP Cahya 2004).

2.5 Empowerment and Poverty Alleviation

According to Sunyoto (1998) in Wasito (2010) to implement the strategy of community development requires a transformation of the role of initiator local government turned into a facilitator. This new paradigm shift in development strategy set offered, among others; strengthen, improve and create the institutional capacity of production, income and expenditure; improve and involving community participation in development planning; distribute the results of development of, by and for the community facilitated by the Government; and increasing the development focused on the human ability (capacity building) which is fostered by the community through empowerment strategies. Mangantar and Baramuli (2016) says that the poor must be heard his voice in decisions concerning their fate in government budget allocations, in program design, in the implementation of programs in the public sector. The programs that reach poor people should be able to give them at least the same number of options granted to the non-poor, and instead of confining the poor solely as government targets

2.6 Empowerment and Government Commitment

Sumodiningrat (2000), the poor are generally characterized by helplessness or inability (powerlessness) in terms of: meeting basic needs such as food and nutrition, clothing, housing, education and health (basic need deprivation, do economically productive activities (unproductiveness) , Reaching social resources and economic (inaccessibility), to determine their fate themselves and constantly receive discriminatory treatment, have feelings of fear and suspicion, as well as apathy and fatalistic (vulnerability); and to free themselves from mental culture of the poor and always felt has dignity and self (Waskito 2010).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Method of Data Collection

This study is categorized as explanatory research is research that aims to explain the causal relationship between the variables through hypothesis testing. This research approach is a survey approach. Paradigm underlying the form of regression and correlation study, the statistical analysis technique called Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Location of the research study was conducted at the Fishermen Society Coastal South Minahasa Regency. The population in the implementation of the research is Fisherman working on the coast numbered around 250 fishermen. This research was taken precision sampling 5% to maintain a representative of the study sample. Sample of 153 people. This study used a questionnaire as an instrument to collect data from respondents, as a method to leverage the data in this research survey. The scale of measurement used on this study is the Likert scale. Tests conducted research tools based on testing Validity and Reliability Test Program using Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 19

3.2 Method of Data analysis

Inferential statistic methods used in the analysis of this research is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). SEM Analysis Techniques Data obtained and the respondent in use as sample through questionnaires in the spread, will be analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on AMOS 4.01 program and SPSS 19.0. AMOS Model shows the measurements of structural problems, and are used to test the hypothesized model.

3.3 Data Analysis and Discussion

Characteristics of respondents include education level, income level and duration of work. Respondents by education level of Fishermen Coastal South Minahasa generally have high levels of standard education in primary schools with the number of 127 (84.6%), SMP (=Junior High School) amounted to 14 people (9%), SMA(= Senior High School) amounting to 8 people (5%) and graduates numbered 1 person (0.8%). This indicates that the tendency of coastal fishing communities is to have a primary school education level. Respondents by income level in Coastal South Minahasa highest numbered 79 people (69%) have income levels of 1000.000-2000.000 per month. 500.000-1000.000 income level amounted to 51 (34%) and income level > 4000,000 numbered 1 (0.8%). When examined more deeply level was slightly below the average of the daily living needs. It takes the role of the government to pay attention to the living conditions of coastal communities. Undergraduate education level is only one person it is because the labor as fishermen is one group of fishermen secretary entrusted by the government to manage the results of cultivation of marine fisheries and coordinating all the groups of fishermen on the seashores.

Respondents based on years of service shows that coastal fishermen have experience as a fisherman catching fish. Fisherman has a service life of > 10 years amounted to 117 people (80.8%), 5-10 Year totaled 24 people (12.8%) and 1-5 years amounted to 9 (6.4%). This result proves that basically coast Fishermen already have experience in working. The results of field observations showed that coastal fishermen in South Minahasa in the subject as a fisherman fishing has a

lot of experience, but when viewed in a state of well-being is still far below the average. The concept of community in empowering potentials that exist around the neighborhood is still underutilized.

Description of the results of research conducted on coastal fishermen community with research sites in South Minahasa take three research areas, namely Kawangkoan village, Teep village and Tatapaan Bajo rural and coastal communities. The distance between the study area and the South Minahasa District province namely Manado and Amurang around 65 Km. The existence of coastal fishermen in the living conditions somewhat different. The location in the village Teep coastal communities economic level is quite high, with some surrounding coastal areas began to be a pilot village in exploiting the potential of the region around, the condition of the area Kawangkoan coastal environment seen polluted where scattered so much trash the poorly cleaned and utilization of the environment yet do. Location Bajo and around the village area still seems to be not well ordered society where poverty rates are high. The results of the analysis of the validity and reliability show that these three variables valid and Reliable.

3.4 Hypothesis Testing Results

There are two pathways direct influence and one significant correlation. Human Resources Strategic have a direct and significant influence on the government's commitment, empowerment has a direct and significant effect on the commitment of the government and there is a positive relationship between strategic human resources with employee empowerment in improving the government's commitment to eradicate poverty coastal fishermen South Minahasa community.

Hypotheses 1. The results indicate that the strategic role of human resources significantly to the government's commitment to these results it can be seen that the results of the analysis of structural models of SEM on a direct influence on the regression coefficient variable strategic role human resources obtained value estimate for 0714 by Critical Ratio of 2.232 and the value of $P < 0.05$, then hypothesis 1 is accepted. The coefficient is positive for 0714 indicate the direct influence of strategic human resources and commitment to perform government is positive. This means that the higher positioned human resources higher the government's commitment.

Hypothesis 2. The result shows that a significant empowerment of the government's commitment. These results can be seen that the results of structural analysis models regression coefficient SEM direct influence on empowerment variables derived estimate for 0873 by Critical Ratio of 2879 and a P value of < 0.05 , the second hypothesis is accepted. The coefficient is positive for 0873 indicate the direct influence of empowerment and commitment of the government is positive. This means that the higher the higher the empowerment of government commitment.

Hypothesis 3. The results showed that the correlation between the role of Strategic Human Resource Empowerment against significant. The results of structural analysis SEM results obtained correlation coefficient of 0.34 with a value of 1.655 and $P < 0.05$ then third hypothesis is accepted. The coefficient is positive at 0.34 indicates that strategic of Human Resources has a positive relationship. Strategic of Human Resources will increase Empowerment

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Human resources Strategy and commitment of the Government

The results of the SEM analysis of structural models obtained significant and positive influence between strategic human resources against the government's commitment. Strategic Human Resource estimate values obtained for 0714 by Critical Ratio of 2.232 and $P < 0.05$, then hypothesis 1 is accepted. Strategic human resources best to achieved when there is an increase in the government's commitment to implement them. The government's role in alleviating poverty in coastal communities is needed by fishermen. In this case the government should be open and have communication with the public. One of the strategic of Human Resources is covering agents of change. As an agent of change the government should change the paradigm of systems and fishing communities about improving people's welfare. The research proves the strategic role Human resources influence on the level of government commitment to improve the quality of human resources. Basically, the community has a role as a change agent to improve its economic prosperity. The existence of human resources in changing environmental conditions can't be denied, therefore demanded high adaptability so that they are not crushed by the change itself. To anticipate and respond to such changes, according to (Tjutju, 2008) there are four main strategies for change, namely by: control themselves better accompanied by wisdom, to adapt to the changes that occurred while changing the paradigm of thinking and acting, effective communication to build trust and develop networking. From the results obtained by the government that sharing is relatively less. This needs to be increased again because if this factor will certainly affect less attention than the sustainability of government programs for coastal fishermen. Based on the results obtained in the communication some respondents revealed that for the provision of government assistance to fishermen who accept are those who are said to have a sufficient economic level means that there is also relief is not appropriate. This is because communication and information point relatively less they earn. Government needs to make a commitment to be honest and direct supervision of the team should be formed to audit the implementation of the programs. Besides, the respondents also said that the strengthening of Human Resources on coastal fishermen today is still relatively weak, which specialized trainings on business management is not maximized so

that they lack knowledge more to harness the potential of natural resources. These results reinforce the notion Noe, 2005 that the strategic role Human resources contribution is the evidence-based management. This can be done by the government for its involvement as a human resource base on evidence. By showing that the practices of human resources has a positive influence on stakeholders (fishermen as part of community and authority).

4.2. Empowerment and Government Commitment

The results of the SEM analysis of structural models obtained significant and positive influence between the empowerment of the government's commitment. The results showed that the government's commitment obtained the empowerment of human resources estimate for 0.873 by Critical Ratio of 2.879 and a P value of <0.05, the second hypothesis is accepted. Empowerment will increase the government's commitment. The results support the research developed by Zefane and Zarooni, 2008 said that significant empowerment in organizational commitment. Empowerment is a process of participation in developing the expertise to make a change. The results support the Etzioni (1986) says that the commitment is seen as a control structure that provides individual empowerment opportunities so that a person chooses their own destination. From the results obtained also that the treatment be tried less. Is one of the factors that need to be considered by the government of South Minahasa District.

4.3. Strategic Human Resource and Empowerment

The results of structural analysis SEM results obtained correlation coefficient of 0.34 with a value of 1.655 and $P < 0.05$ then third hypothesis is accepted. The coefficient is positive at 0.34 indicates that strategic human resources has a positive relationship. Human resources Strategic Empowerment will increase. The results support the findings of a study by Kang and Steward (2006) says that the development of human resources has a relationship with empowerment. They were also revealed that human resource development and empowerment high. Strategic Human resources is an equal partner in the process of strategic planning. The Role of Human Resources in the Strategy shows that Human resources can play a role as environmental monitoring, Human resources is a unique position to supply intelligence to compete that may be useful in the process of strategic planning, Human resources also participate in the process of strategy formulation by supplying information about the company's internal strengths and weaknesses, strengths and weaknesses of human resources has an effect on the survival of the organization's strategic choice of the government. The Indicators of reinforces empowerment is communication. The findings showed that the indicators of access to information in the form of lines of information provided by the Government to have a low value. These results indicate that the role of government in South Minahasa in providing information should be open and required by coastal fishermen. During this coastal fishermen are less empowered. This is because access to information obtained by the fishermen is comparatively less.

Results of research conducted by the researchers took samples of a several locations in South Minahasa fishing communities around the coast in this case (under Kawangkoan, Teep and Bajo village) results showed the level of education of the dominant coastal fishermen is an elementary school with old works over ten years. The government needs to increase and strengthen Human resources. Human resources in the form of providing training in business management, training on use of the environment. Keep reassessing the problem assistance given to fishermen based on complaints encountered in the field are not well targeted assistance. The facilities were already there did not used as a supposed, is seen from the buildings and facilities are not maintained as well as the lack of activity (needed an evaluation facilities and infrastructure improvements).

The government's commitment to provide assistance to communities around the beach needs to be monitored and evaluated. Honest commitment in the form of a given administration should be equitably to people not only in the community groups already established economies resulting the social gap. The result of the assistance provided actually on the economy in the society in terms of revenue is relatively less.

It provides access to the right information and open (online publication) and compiles a database of fishermen according to income level. Creating an evidence-based Human Resources through the preparation of Administrative clear as a role model behavior human resources. Need to empowerment coastal fishermen in increasing economic prosperity.

Need to utilize the potential of natural resources in coastal areas by providing opportunities for coastal fishermen to develop the creativity of its business by providing capital assistance.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The indicators most strongly affect strategic Human resources is an agent of change. Indicators of commitment honesty, commitment to fairness, commitment to accountability and commitment significantly confidence measure variables government commitment. Indicators of confidence in the commitment of the commitment item on the promise of the most powerful measure of government commitment. Indicators of access to information, opportunities, involvement and communication significantly affect the variable empowerment. Indicators of empowerment is most strongly affect communication on openness item.

The results showed that the strategic Human resources has a positive influence and significant against the government's commitment. This means that the higher positioned Human resources higher the government's commitment to enhance the participation of fishermen in improving the economic welfare of society by becoming agents of change in a changing society's idea to develop the potential of natural resources.

The study found that empowerment has a positive and significant impact on the government's commitment. This means that empowerment will increase the government's commitment. Increased empowerment means giving power and greater responsibility on coastal fishermen in the improvement of their welfare. Commitment is honest and open government should continue to be made in helping communities improve the capacity of community life.

The study found that strategic human resources have a positive and significant relationship with empowerment. Human resources strategic meaning has a strong relationship with empowerment. Empowerment is not limited to training and development activities. Rather non training empowerment is an intervention in the form of providing information, business opportunities, involvement in decision making so as to increase capacity in the strategy human resources.

Sharing information on the public and government attention needs to be effected coast again by giving special attention to the low economic society in the form of income poverty, poor information and poor knowledge

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